

INNOVATIVE
WORLD

ORIENTAL JOURNAL OF MEDICINE AND NATURAL SCIENCES

- Medicine
- Pharmaceuticals
- Biology
- Chemistry
- Geology
- Agriculture

JANUARY
2024

Volume 1
Issue 1

+998 94 5668868

www.inno-world.uz

MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE VENTRICULAR AND ATRIUM MYOCARDIUM

Mansurova Dilorom Aslanovna

Senior lecturer of the Department of Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Alfraganus University

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th January 2024

Accepted: 15th January 2024

Online: 15th January 2024

KEY WORDS

heart of rat pups, postnatal ontogenesis, cardiomyocytes, fibrous structure of the atrium and ventricles.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of our work was to identify the features of morphogenesis in postnatal ontogenesis, to study the histological structure of different parts and membranes of the heart of rat pups on days 1-22 after birth. The object of the study was the heart of 50 rat pups on days 1, 6, 11, 16, and 22 after birth. There is an alternation of periods of accelerated and slow increases in the growth rate of the thickness of the atrium and ventricles. The thickness of the endocardium and epicardium increases less significantly. The growth rate of ventricular myocardial thickness is observed in rat pups 6 and 16 days of age. Structural transformations occur due to the growth of the organism itself. A feature of the structure and topography of cardiac microvessels is their distribution along the course of cardiomyocytes and their relationship with the fibrous structures of the connective tissue of cardiomyocytes.

Relevance of the topic. Analysis of the latest data shows that cardiovascular pathology remains the main cause of mortality in all developed world [1,2,3,5]. The heart is most often exposed to pathological effects of endogenous and exogenous irritants, as a result of which not only its function is impaired, but also various pathological processes develop throughout the body. The heart of animals and humans can adapt and change depending on lifestyle and the overall load on the body [7]. The age-related structure of the heart has a certain significance in revealing some pathological processes developing in it. Also, in the pathogenesis of many diseases of the cardiovascular system, the connective tissue component of the myocardium plays a leading role; it is the most dynamic component in the heart in the process of morphogenesis and pathogenesis [4,6,8]. Therefore, a deep and comprehensive study of the structure of the walls of the heart and its connective tissue component is relevant and justifiably determined the choice of direction for our research. The rat heart is a convenient model for experimental research, and also obtains a sufficient amount of material for study.

Purpose of the study. Identification of features of morphogenesis and study of the histological structure of different parts and membranes of the heart of rat pups in early postnatal ontogenesis.

Materials and methods of research. The hearts of 50 rat pups were studied on days 1, 6, 11, 16, and 22 after birth. In each age group, the hearts of 10 rat pups were examined. The animals were kept in standard vivarium conditions at 21-22°C and natural daylight on a normal diet. Experimental studies were carried out in accordance with the "Rules for carrying out work using experimental animals". The slaughter of rat pups was performed under ether anesthesia. After opening the chest and abdominal cavities, the material was fixed in a 12% solution of neutral formalin, then the heart was isolated. After fixation, the heart was removed and washed for 1 day in running water. Afterwards the organ was carried out on alcohols of increasing concentration. The organ was then divided into the atrium and ventricles and embedded in paraffin. Histological sections with a thickness of 8-10 microns were prepared from paraffin blocks. Sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin using the Van Gieson and Weigert methods and impregnation using the Foote method modified by N.A. Yurina. Morphometric measurements of the wall thickness of the atrium and ventricles were made using an eyepiece ruler at a microscope magnification of vol.90, approx.7. Processing of mathematical data was carried out using Microsoft Excel 2010 applications in the section of descriptive statistics, determination of standard deviations, arithmetic mean M , average error of relative values m . Data were accepted as reliable at $P < 0.05$.

Results of our own research. The atrial wall of the heart of rat pups is characterized by uneven thickness. Analysis of the table shows that the thickness of the left and right atria increases gradually over the entire period of the study. At 6 days of age in rat pups, the increase in wall thickness of the left and right atrium compared to newborns is 14% and 11%. At 11 days of age, compared with 6 day old rat pups, the increase in the thickness of the left atrium was 21% and the right atrium was 14%. In 16-day-old rat pups 18% and 13%. The rate of increase in the thickness of the left and right atrium in rat pups 22 days of age increases almost equally and amounts to 20% and 19%. The thickness of the endocardium of the left and right atrium is not the same in all stages of ontogenesis, greater in the left atrium, less in the right. The endocardium of the atria of the heart of rat pups is represented by a single layer of endothelial cells. The nuclei of endothelial cells have a round shape (Figure 1). In the endocardium of the atria, bundles of collagen fibers have different densities. The bundles of connective tissue fibers lying closer to the lumen of the atria are located loosely, the bundles lying next to the atrial myocardium are more tightly adjacent to each other. And they are intertwined with bundles of connective tissue fibers from the inner layer of cardiomyocytes of the atrial myocardium. The thickness of the collagen fiber bundles in the endocardium ranges from 5.7 μm to 7.6 μm . In the endocardium, the thickness of the elastic fiber bundles varies from 3.8 to 7.6 μm . Reticular fibers throughout the atrial endocardium have varying densities. They are

intertwined with reticular fibers from the connective tissue layers located between the bundles of cardiomyocytes of the inner layer of the atrium myocardium.

Fig.1. Endothelial cells of the wall of the left atrium of the heart of 6-day-old rats in the control group. UV: approx. 10, ob. 20.

The rat atrium myocardium is represented by two layers of cardiomyocytes. It consists of superficially longitudinally located and deep circularly directed muscle layers. The bundles of cardiomyocytes lying next to the endocardium change direction and are located obliquely. In the outer layer, bundles of cardiomyocytes are located longitudinally. In the atrial myocardium, the boundary between the layers of cardiomyocytes is poorly defined. They are adjacent to each other. Throughout the myocardium, bundles of cardiomyocytes in the layers change direction and penetrate each other.

Atrial cardiomyocytes are surrounded by bundles of fibrous connective tissue structures. In the atrial myocardium, depending on the area, their different directions are revealed. In the inner layer of the myocardium, bundles of collagen fibers lie in a circular direction between bundles of cardiomyocytes. Deep in the inner layer of the myocardium, the fibrous structure of the connective tissue changes direction and is located perpendicular to the endocardium of the atrium. At the periphery of the outer muscle layer, connective tissue bundles change direction from longitudinal to oblique and intertwine with bundles from the epicardium. At the border of the outer and inner layers of the atria myocardium there are areas where the fibrous structures of the connective tissue are intertwined. The thickness of the collagen fiber bundles between the cardiomyocyte bundles ranges from 5.7 to 11.4 μm . The thickness of the elastic fiber bundles is from 3.8 microns to 11.4 microns. Reticular fibers in the atrial myocardium lie in the connective tissue layers between bundles of cardiomyocytes. Reticular fibers are located along the cardiomyocytes, forming loops of various shapes and sizes. A high density of reticular fibers

is detected between the bundles of cardiomyocytes of the inner layer of the atrium.

A study of the structure of the wall of the interatrial septum showed that the septum is formed by the walls of both atria. In the epicardium of the atria, bundles of elastic fibers lie loosely compared to bundles of collagen fibers. In the epicardium of the atria, the thickness of the collagen fiber bundles ranges from 5.7 to 7.6 μm , the thickness of the elastic fiber bundles varies from 3.8 to 7.6 μm . Reticular fibers in the epicardium of the atria are located more densely.

The ventricular endocardium consists of longitudinally directed bundles of collagen fibers. The places where longitudinally lying bundles of collagen fibers are intertwined with each other are identified. Bundles of connective tissue fibers located closer to the ventricular myocardium are intertwined with bundles of connective tissue fibers located between the bundles of cardiomyocytes in the inner layer of the myocardium.

The thickness of the collagen fiber bundles of the ventricular endocardium ranges from 5.7 μm to 11.4 μm . Bundles of elastic fibers of the ventricular endocardium lie loosely compared to bundles of collagen fibers. The density of the fiber bundles adjacent to the ventricular myocardium increases. The thickness of the elastic fiber bundles of the ventricles ranges from 5.7 to 9.5 microns. Reticular fibers in the ventricular endocardium are located close to each other (Figure 2).

The myocardium of the ventricles of the heart is represented by 3 layers of cardiomyocytes. The outer, subepicardial layer contains cardiomyocytes that form longitudinal bundles; in the middle layer, circularly oriented bundles are found; the inner subendocardial layer contains slightly obliquely oriented bundles of cardiomyocytes. The outer and inner longitudinally directed layers belong to both ventricles. Superficially located fibers cover both ventricles evenly. As they approach the endocardium, the internal bundles of fibers acquire a more oblique direction and pass into the papillary muscles. The middle circular layer belongs to only one of the ventricles. A study of the direction of the fiber bundles of the ventricular myocardium showed that the circularly directed layer does not always have a clear orientation. The bundles of fibers of the middle layer on the anterior wall of the ventricles are directed obliquely and deviate towards the endocardium. The border between the layers of cardiomyocytes of the ventricular myocardium is poorly defined. They fit tightly to each other. In the middle layer, bundles of cardiomyocytes are arranged circularly. Bundles of cardiomyocytes located near the inner layer of the myocardium change direction from longitudinal to oblique.

Rice. 2. Reticular fibers of the endocardium of the lateral wall of the left ventricle at 6 days of age in the control group. Impregnation with silver nitrate according to Foote as modified by Yurina. UV: approx. 10, ob. 20.

In the border areas with the middle layer of the myocardium in the outer layer, some of the cardiomyocyte bundles begin to change direction from longitudinal to oblique. In the left ventricle, there is no significant difference in the thickness of the cardiomyocyte layers. The inner layer of the myocardium consists of parallel bundles of cardiomyocytes running parallel to the endocardium. The outer layer of the myocardium has a loose and bundle-like structure, in which cardiomyocytes are located in different directions. In the middle layer of the myocardium of the left ventricle of the heart, bundles of cardiomyocytes are located perpendicular to the inner layer. In the center of cardiomyocytes there is an oval-shaped nucleus, in the amount of 1-2. The nucleus of cardiomyocytes is located in the center of the cell, and myofibrils are located at the periphery. In the right ventricle, bundles of cardiomyocytes in the layers of the myocardium are similar to the myocardium of the left ventricle. But unlike the left ventricle, in the myocardium of the right ventricle the thickness of the circular layer of cardiomyocytes is 2-3 times thinner than the thickness of the longitudinal layers of cardiomyocytes. The nucleus of cardiomyocytes was distinguished by its elongated shape. In places, arterioles are found in the middle layer of the myocardium. The outer layer of the myocardium contains a large number of venules with various shapes.

In the myocardium of the ventricles of the heart, depending on the area, bundles of collagen fibers have different directions. At the apex of the heart, bundles of collagen fibers are directed obliquely; some bundles of collagen fibers change direction from oblique to longitudinal. In the inner layer of the myocardium, bundles of collagen fibers lie in the longitudinal direction, separating bundles of cardiomyocytes from each other. In the middle layer

of the myocardium between the bundles of cardiomyocytes, collagen fibers form bundles that have a circular direction. In the outer layer of the myocardium, bundles of collagen fibers lie obliquely between bundles of cardiomyocytes. The thickness of the collagen fiber bundles in the ventricular myocardium varies from 7.6 μm to 13.3 μm .

Reticular fibers in the ventricular myocardium have different directions depending on its layer. In the inner layer, the reticular fibers lie longitudinally; in the region of the apex of the heart they intertwine with reticular fibers from the outer layer of the myocardium of the heart. In the middle layer of the myocardium, reticular fibers between bundles of cardiomyocytes are located in a circular direction. In the outer layer of the ventricular myocardium, reticular fibers lie obliquely; in the region of the apex of the heart, the density of their arrangement increases. Reticular and elastic fibers around bundles of cardiomyocytes form a network of various sizes and shapes. The direction of the connecting fiber bundles depends on the direction of the cardiomyocytes. They envelop individual muscle bundles, forming loops of various shapes and sizes. In the myocardium, bundles of reticular and elastic fibers are directed along the bundles of cardiomyocytes.

The interventricular septum consists of two longitudinal and one circular layer. The longitudinal layers on the left and right are formed from the corresponding longitudinal layers of both ventricles, and the middle circular layer is formed from the circular layer of the left ventricle of the heart (Figure 3). The ventricular myocardium contains arterioles, capillaries, venules and sinusoids. Arterioles at this age are characterized by a thin inner tunica, a clearly defined middle tunica, and a weakly defined outer tunica. The inner lining of the arteriole is represented by the nuclei of endothelial cells in a rounded shape; they are located at a small distance from each other. A clearly defined tunica media consists of circularly directed bundles of muscle fibers. They form two layers. The outer shell is formed by loose fibrous tissue and contains adventitial cells. The thickness of the internal diameter ranges from 9.5 to 15.2 μm , with an average of $11.7 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{m}$.

Pic.3. Interventricular septum, heart of a 6-day-old rat in the control group. Staining: hematoxylin and eosin. UV: approx. 10, ob. 20.

Myocardial venules in most cases are represented by sinusoids of various diameters and different shapes. The wall of the venules is represented by endothelial cells, which are located at a great distance from each other. The muscular layer of the venules is poorly developed. The thickness of the venules ranges from 15.7 to 20.5 μm . Myocardial sinusoids have an elongated, oval or irregular shape. Sinusoids occur in the subepicardial layer. The wall of the sinusoids consists of a single layer of endothelial cells. In most cases, endothelial cells are elongated.

The capillary wall is composed of endothelial cells. The nuclei of endothelial cells are round and oval in shape. They are located at a small distance from each other. The thickness of the internal diameter of the capillaries ranges from 5.7 to 11.4 microns, on average 9.3 ± 0.6 .

In the epicardium of the ventricles of the heart, bundles of collagen and elastic fibers lie longitudinally and have a greater density of arrangement than bundles of collagen and elastic fibers of the endocardium. In the ventricular epicardium, the thickness of the collagen fiber bundles varies from 5.7 μm to 11.4 μm , and the elastic fiber bundles have a thickness from 5.7 μm to 9.5 μm . In the epicardium of the ventricles, reticular fibers are located longitudinally.

Analysis of the table shows that the thickness of the lower part of the ventricle always prevails over the upper part. The thickness of the right wall of the ventricles is always less than the right side. The increase in wall thickness most occurs on days 6 and 16 after birth; their increase is 27% and 22% in the left ventricle, and 19% and 15% in the right ventricle. On the 11th day, the increase in thickness decreases to 14% of the left ventricle, and 11% of the right. On the 22nd day after birth, the increase in the thickness of the left and right ventricles is 21 and 16%, respectively.

Conclusions:

1. The results of the study indicate that at the time of birth, the hearts of white rats are not completely differentiated; their development continues after birth.
2. In the myocardium, blood vessels are directed along the bundles of cardiomyocytes. The vessels are surrounded by paravasal bundles of connective tissue. There is almost no difference in the diameter of intraorgan vessels in the walls of the left and right ventricles.
3. Superficially located fibers cover the left and right ventricles evenly. As they approach the endocardium, the internal bundles of myocardial fibers acquire a more oblique direction and pass into trabeculae and papillary muscles. The middle layer consists of circularly directed bundles of cardiomyocytes, which belong to only one of the ventricles.

Literature.

1. Akhmedova S.M. Morphological characteristics of the development of the walls of the heart of rat pups. *Science and Peace*. 2015; 1(7): 85-87.
2. Akhmedova S. M. Creation of the informational model of toxic myocarditis occurred under the influence of pesticides // *European science review*, Austria, Vienna, 2015. - No. 11-12. - R. 61-63
3. Akhmedova S. M. Histological structure of rat heart in the early stages of ontogeny // *European science review*, Austria, Vienna, 2016. - No. 5-6. - R. 30-33.
4. Akhmedova S.M., Mirsharapov U.M. Some morphofunctional changes of heart at the influence of pesticides. *Bulletin of the Doctor* No. 2—2018: 15-18
5. Bockeria O.L., Akhobekov A.A. Sudden cardiac death: mechanisms of occurrence and risk stratification. *Annals of Arrhythmology*. 2012; 3:5-13.
6. Boldueva S.A. , Shabrov A.V., Lebedev D.S. and others. Prediction and prevention of sudden cardiac death in patients who have had myocardial infarction. *Cardiovascular therapy and prevention*. 2008; 7(3): 56-62.
7. Gorbunov A.A. The connective tissue component of the myocardium: a new stage in the study of a long-standing problem. *Morphology*. 2007; 4:6-12.
8. Kurbanov R.D., Mullabaeva G.U., Kilichev A.A., Kevorkova Yu.G., Sayfitdinova N.B. Efficacy of ivabradine in the treatment of patients with Q-wave myocardial infarction. *Cardiology of Uzbekistan*. 2014; 3: 11-16.
9. Lebedinets A.N., Voloshin N.A., Chugin S.V. Dynamics of structural components of the heart of rats in the postnatal period after intrauterine exposure to antigens of various natures. *Pathology*. 2011; 2:43-45.
10. Chirkova E. N. Morphology of the heart and its internal structures of mammals of different ecological groups (dissertation). Orenburg 2009.
11. Michela N. F. Inform the Heart: Control of Cardiomyocyte Cycling and Size by Age-Dependent Paracrine Signals. *Developmental Cell*. 2009; 16:161.